

Environmental inequalities and climate racism: the relationship between economic growth, GHG emissions, and their social impacts in Goiás and Brazil (2000-2020)

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Abstract

The increase in global temperature due to Greenhouse Gas (GHG) emissions is one of the main challenges of the 21st century. The Paris Agreement (2015) aims to limit global warming to 2°C by 2030, reducing emissions. However, economic growth, crucial for emerging countries like Brazil, drives these emissions. This research analyzes GHG emissions in Brazil and Goiás (2000-2020), focusing on environmental inequalities and their socioeconomic impacts. The hypothesis is that GDP growth intensifies emissions, creating a dilemma between economic growth and sustainability. To mitigate environmental inequalities, Brazil and Goiás must invest in clean technologies and renewable energy, prioritizing climate justice and environmental racism. The energy transition must be inclusive, considering regional and social inequalities to prevent worsening environmental injustices.

Keywords: Economic Growth. Greenhouse Gases. Environmental Racism. Renewable Energy. Environmental Inequalities.

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Introduction

Economic growth is a central objective for countries, as it is directly related to the generation of wealth and the well-being of the population. To this end, governments adopt various development strategies, many of which depend on the intensification of the use of fossil fuels. However, the burning of these resources is the main cause of carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, the most significant of the Greenhouse Gases (GHG), driving global warming and, consequently, climate change. The greenhouse effect can be defined as a natural phenomenon (Almeida, 2016). It is responsible for energy balance through the constant flow of energy that the Earth absorbs and radiates.

Climate change represents one of the greatest challenges of the 21st century, affecting different social groups and regions unequally. The increase in global temperature, driven by GHG emissions, has intensified extreme weather events and deepened environmental inequalities. Both developed and developing countries emit greenhouse gases; for the purpose of this article, we do not differentiate between these emissions because the impacts of rising temperatures are global. We focus the study on Brazil, and specifically in the state of Goiás, the relationship between economic growth and GHG emissions raises a fundamental dilemma: how to reconcile development and sustainability without aggravating socio-environmental injustices?

Understanding this relationship requires an in-depth analysis of the greenhouse effect and how it is intensified by human activities. According to Almeida (2016), the greenhouse effect is a natural phenomenon in which part of the solar energy reflected by the Earth's surface is absorbed by certain atmospheric gases, retaining heat and preventing its dispersion into space. Xavier and Kerr (2004) add that these gases, although invisible to solar radiation, reflect part of the Sun's ultraviolet radiation and the infrared radiation emitted by the Earth, in a phenomenon called infrared trapping³.

Global concern about the environmental impacts of economic growth gained momentum in the 1970s, following discussions promoted by the Club of Rome. According to Romeiro (2012), the report *The Limits to Growth* (1972) warned of the need to curb unbridled economic growth to avoid the depletion of natural resources and worsening pollution, which could drastically compromise the population's quality of life. In response to these challenges, in 1987, the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED), known as the Brundtland Commission, presented the report *Our Common Future*, developed by the United Nations (UN). The document highlighted the importance of sustainable development, which seeks to balance economic growth and environmental conservation, ensuring that the needs of the present are met without compromising future generations (FEIL and SCHREIBER,

³ The Earth exchanges heat with the atmosphere, which prevents the planet from cooling or heating excessively, thus affecting life. Disturbances in this balance can alter the dynamics of life, and the increase in greenhouse gas emissions caused by human activities is having an impact, due to the fact that CO₂ remains suspended in the atmosphere, affecting heat exchange.

2017). However, as pointed out by Romeiro (2012), the emergence of the problem of global warming in the 1990s highlighted a trade-off between economic growth and environmental preservation. Rapid reductions in GHG emissions can impose high costs on economies, as they limit the expansion of production and consumption of energy from non-renewable sources.

Given this scenario, this research investigates GHG emissions in Brazil and Goiás between 2000 and 2020, analyzing their social and economic impacts, with a special focus on environmental inequalities and climate racism. The central hypothesis suggests that GDP growth drives emissions, resulting in an unequal distribution of environmental impacts, which disproportionately affect vulnerable populations.

The conceptual framework: the case of Brazil

In 1997, the signatory countries signed the Kyoto Protocol, committing them to reduce their greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The treaty established that industrialized countries should reduce their combined emissions by at least 5.2% compared to 1990 levels. Although Brazil was not required to meet strict targets due to its status as a developing country, it voluntarily adhered to the Kyoto Protocol. According to Euler (2016), even in the face of social and economic challenges, the country achieved one of the largest individual reduction efforts, reducing its emissions by more than 41% in 2012 compared to 2005 levels.

With the expiration of the Kyoto Protocol in 2015, Brazil joined the Paris Agreement, committing to reduce emissions and limit the increase in global temperature to 1.5°C by 2030. In a global context, Brazil, having started its industrialization process relatively late, from the 1930s onwards, has not accumulated historical emissions on the same scale as the major powers. Furthermore, the national energy matrix has a significant share of renewable sources, such as hydroelectric power. In response to the First Oil Shock (1973), the country developed a biofuels program based on sugarcane ethanol, a less polluting alternative compared to fossil fuels.

However, Brazil's economic trajectory has historically been tied to the exploitation of natural resources. Since the colonial period, economic cycles have been driven by activities such as logging, sugar, gold, rubber and coffee cycles. Brazil's insertion in international trade was consolidated through the export of primary products, such as soybeans and beef, which are responsible for a large part of national emissions, mainly due to deforestation and changes in land use.

In 2019, renewable sources represented 46.1% of Brazil's energy matrix, a percentage significantly higher than the average for countries in the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), which was 10.8%, and the world average, which was 14.2%. In the electricity sector, this participation was even more expressive, reaching 83%, while the OECD average was 28.5% and the world average was 26.7% (MINISTRY OF SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND INNOVATIONS, 2021).

Environmental Racism and Regional Inequalities in GHG Emissions

Despite the high share of renewable sources in the energy matrix, the distribution of environmental impacts and economic benefits resulting from GHG emissions in Brazil is unequal. The concept of environmental racism, introduced by Bullard (1993), refers to the disproportionate distribution of environmental damages on historically marginalized populations, often without access to adequate infrastructure and effective public policies to mitigate impacts. This environmental inequality is reflected in the relationship between GDP and GHG emissions. In Brazil, economically more dynamic regions, such as the Southeast, concentrate most of the industrial activity, while states in the Central-West, such as Goiás, have their emissions strongly linked to agribusiness and changes in land use. Goiás, for example, had significant GDP growth driven by the agricultural sector and deforestation for the expansion of pastures and crops. However, the benefits of this growth were not equally distributed: quilombola communities, indigenous peoples and rural populations often suffer the greatest environmental impacts, including water scarcity, soil degradation and pesticide contamination.

The relationship between GDP and GHG emissions in Goiás illustrates a classic dilemma of sustainable development: while increased economic activity drives the state's growth, it also intensifies environmental inequalities. This reinforces the need for public policies that integrate climate justice into economic planning, ensuring that development does not occur at the expense of the most vulnerable populations.

Therefore, this research seeks to deepen the analysis of how economic growth in Goiás and Brazil impacts different social groups, highlighting the challenges of achieving a development model that is both sustainable and socially just.

2. Analysis and discussion of results.

Figure 1 – Emissions graph for Brazil and Goiás (2000–2020).

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

The graph shows greenhouse gas emissions (in tons) for Brazil and Goiás. Note that emissions for both locations vary significantly, with peaks in years such as 2004-2005 and reductions in subsequent years.

Goiás shows smaller fluctuations compared to Brazil, which shows sharp drops after 2005 and further reductions until 2020.

Why is there no relationship with GDP? Despite the variations in emissions, the GDP of Goiás and Brazil (observed in other images) follows a trend of constant growth over the years. This shows that GDP is not directly affected by emissions, since there is economic growth even in periods when emissions fall, reducing advances in cleaner technologies and greater productive efficiency.

Figure 2 – GDP and emissions graphs for Brazil (2000–2020).

Source: Authors’ own elaboration.

Brazil’s GDP has shown almost continuous growth, rising from approximately R\$1.2 trillion in 2000 to approximately R\$8.7 trillion in 2020. The emissions graphs, however, show a peak in 2004-2005, followed by a significant decline until 2010 and smoother fluctuations thereafter.

Analysis of the disconnect: Although Brazil’s GDP has been increasing steadily, emissions have declined significantly since 2005 and have remained at lower levels. This suggests that Brazil has managed to grow economically while reducing its emissions, probably through the adoption of external public policies to reduce deforestation and increase the efficiency in the use of natural resources.

Figura 3 - Gráficos do PIB e emissões de Goiás (2000-2020)

Source: Authors' own elaboration.

Goiás follows the same trend as Brazil in terms of GDP, showing constant growth from R\$39 billion in 2000 to R\$270 billion in 2020. GHG emissions, however, show more marked fluctuations, with a peak in 2004-2005, followed by a decline until 2010 and a stabilization with an increase until 2020.

Justification for the lack of relationship: Goiás' economic growth occurred independently of emissions. This suggests that the state managed to increase its economic output without proportionally increasing its GHG emissions, possibly due to the modernization of the agricultural sector (which is one of the main sectors in Goiás) and the adoption of more sustainable practices.

The data analyzed show that greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in Brazil and Goiás showed significant variations between 2000 and 2020. Brazil had significant peaks between 2004 and 2005, followed by a continuous reduction until 2010 and moderate fluctuations thereafter. Goiás showed a similar behavior, but with milder fluctuations over the years. These patterns indicate that, despite fluctuations in emissions, there were efforts to mitigate the environmental impact, possibly due to policies to control deforestation and the advancement of more efficient production practices.

However, when analyzing the relationship between GDP and emissions, a clear disconnect is observed. Brazil's GDP grew steadily, going from approximately R\$1.2 trillion in 2000 to approximately R\$8.7 trillion in 2020, even in periods when emissions fell. Goiás followed a similar trend, increasing its GDP from R\$39 billion to R\$270 billion in the same period. This suggests that economic growth does not directly depend

on increased GHG emissions, reinforcing the hypothesis that technological advances and environmental policies can enable more sustainable development.

Future studies

This article concludes that, in the case of Brazil and the state of Goiás, the increase in GHG emissions is not related to GDP growth. Further studies are needed to identify why GHG emissions increased or decreased during the period 2000-2020.

Final Considerations

The analysis of GHG emissions and GDP reveals an important aspect of environmental inequalities and climate racism. More vulnerable regions, especially low-income communities and indigenous populations, continue to be disproportionately affected by climate change, even though global economic growth is no longer directly linked to increased emissions. This indicates that, although Brazil has reduced its emissions, environmental impacts still fall on historically marginalized groups, reinforcing the need for public policies that guarantee climate justice and social equity.

Goiás, with its strong agricultural economy, has managed to modernize its production without proportionally increasing GHG emissions, but this does not mean that environmental impacts are equally distributed. Small producers and rural communities face challenges in adapting to a more sustainable model, often without the same access to clean technologies as large industries and corporations. Therefore, to ensure truly sustainable development, it is essential that environmental policies be designed with a close eye on regional and social inequalities, preventing the burden of the energy transition from falling on the most vulnerable.

References

ALMEIDA, H. A. de. Capítulo 1: A Atmosfera Terrestre. *Climatol. Apl. a Geogr.* Campina Grande: EDUPB, 2016. p. 19–60.

AZARIADIS, Costas & STACHURSKI, John. "Poverty Traps," in: Aghion, P. & Steven DURLAUF, S (eds.), *Handbook of Economic Growth*, volume 1, chapter 5, Elsevier, 2005.

CMMD, World Commission on Environment on Development. *Our common future*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1987.

EULER, A. M. C. O acordo de Paris e o futuro do REDD+ no Brasil. *Cadernos Adenauer*, v. 2, n. 17, p. 85–104, 2016.

FEIL, A. A. e SCHREIBER, D. Sustentabilidade e desenvolvimento sustentável: desvendando as sobreposições e alcances de seus significados, *Cad. EBAPE.BR* 15 (3). Jul2017. Disponível em: <https://doi.org/10.1590/1679-395157473>. Acesso em 08 de novembro de 2023.

GOVERNO DO ESTADO DE GOIÁS. Conjuntura Econômica Goiana: outubro de 2011. Boletim Trimestral n. 18. Goiânia, 2011. Disponível em: https://sitedom.goias.gov.br/imb/wp-content/uploads/sites/29/2024/01/repositorio_2011_008_conjuntura_economica_goiana_18_dezembro_2011.pdf. Acesso em: 17 jun. 2024.

GUARINI, Júlio; OREIRO, José Luís. Uma visão ecológica do Novo Desenvolvimentismo: uma proposta de integração. *Revista Brasileira de Economia Política*, v. 42, p. 244-255, 2022.

JONES, Charles I.; VOLLARTH, Dietrich. *Introdução à teoria do crescimento econômico*. 3ª Edição. Rio de Janeiro, 2015.

MINISTÉRIO DA CIÊNCIA, TECNOLOGIA E INOVAÇÕES. *Quarta Comunicação Nacional do Brasil à Convenção-Quadro das Nações Unidas sobre Mudança do Clima*. Brasília: 2021. Disponível em: <https://www.gov.br/mcti/pt-br/acompanhe-o-mcti/sirene/publicacoes/comunicacoes-nacionais-do-brasil-a-unfccc>. Acesso em: 17 jun. 2024.

MUELLER, C. C. *Os economistas e as relações entre o sistema econômico e o meio ambiente*. 1ª reimpressão. ed. Brasília: Editora Universidade de Brasília, 2012. 562 p. ISBN 85-230-0850.

ONU – ORGANIZAÇÃO DAS NAÇÕES UNIDAS. *Convenção-Quadro das Nações Unidas para mudanças climáticas: Acordo de Paris*. Paris, 2015.

ROMEIRO. A. R. Desenvolvimento Sustentável: uma perspectiva econômico-ecológica. *Estudos Avançados* (26) 74, 2012.

SISTEMA DE ESTIMATIVAS DE EMISSÕES E REMOÇÕES DE GASES DE EFEITO ESTUFA (SEEG). Disponível em: <https://seeg.eco.br/>. Acesso em: 17 jun. 2024.

XAVIER, M. E. R.; KERR, A. S. A Análise do Efeito Estufa em textos para-didáticos e periódicos jornalísticos. *Cad. Bras. Ens. Fís*, v. 21, n. 3, p. 325–349, 2004.